

DESIGN OF RASPBERRY PI WEB-BASED ENERGY MONITORING SYSTEM FOR RESIDENTIAL ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this project is to develop and deploy a web-based energy monitoring system for residential electricity consumption using Internet of Things (IoT) technology and various hardware elements, including a Raspberry Pi Pico, LCD display, current coil, relay energy meter PZEM004T, ESP8226, and RFID. The planned system will enable households to track their energy usage in real-time via a web-based interface, giving them insights into their energy usage habits and assisting them in finding ways to lower their electricity bills. The device will also compute the electricity rate depending on energy consumption and display it on the LCD screen. The hardware elements will cooperate to track and measure energy use, with the current coil identifying the power theft and give alert to the user via web server or via mobile application. An RFID tag and reader will be used for the purpose of prepaying option, that will display the amount which has been paid by the user. This web-based energy monitoring system will give households an affordable and practical tool to track their energy usage, prepaid amount, lower their electricity bills, and contribute to a more sustainable future.

INTRODUCTION

Over time, residential households' use of electricity has increased, resulting in rising

electricity costs and environmental issues. Energy monitoring devices that enable households to track their energy usage in real-time and find solutions to lower their electricity bills are becoming more and more necessary to address these challenges. In this project, we suggest an Internet of Things (IoT)-based web-based energy monitoring system that makes use of a variety of hardware elements, including Raspberry Pi Pico, LCD display, current coil, relay 3.3, relay energy meter PZEM004T, ESP8226, and RFID, to measure and monitor energy consumption in residential homes. With a web-based interface, the system will enable homeowners to track their energy usage in real-time, giving them insights into their usage patterns and assisting them in finding ways to lower their electricity bills. Also, based on energy consumption, the system will determine the electricity rate and display it on the LCD panel. With the current coil monitoring the current flowing through the circuit and the energy metre PZEM004T measuring the voltage and power consumption, the hardware components will work together to measure and monitor the energy usage. The Raspberry Pi Pico will process and store the data after receiving it wirelessly from the ESP8226 module. Relay 3.3 will manage the power supply to the relay and the energy metre, ensuring that only the essential parts are turned on when required. An RFID card reader will be used to

authenticate the user and guarantee that only permitted users can access the system. Users can check their energy use and tariff information on the LCD panel after swiping their RFID card to gain access to the system. Homeowners will be able to monitor their energy usage, lower their electricity costs, and contribute to a more sustainable future with the help of this web-based energy monitoring system.

Literature survey

This paper presents design and development of a GSM based energy monitoring, profiling and control system. Our system integrates digital energy meters installed at consumer unit with an electric supply company's energy monitoring system. Single phase or three phase digital electric meter can be used with indigenously developed add on transmission module, which takes the meter reading and utilizes the GSM network to transmit the energy usage reading using Short Message Service (SMS) back to the energy supplier. At the supplier end, an energy monitoring system is used to manage all received meter readings, compute the billing cost, update the database and maintain an energy consumption profile for each user. Various alerts and control can also be generated by the supplier. A simple, cost effective and reliable working prototype of complete system has been developed using digital energy meter manufactured by MicroTech Limited, Pakistan to demonstrate an efficient and transparent means of automatic meter reading, billing and notification through the use of GSM network. The conventional metering system requires the supplier company to send personnel who manually read and record the energy consumption, so billing can be done accordingly. The manual reading system

suffers from a wide variety of disadvantages, which tenders it inefficient. It requires a large number of meter readers to collect reading from all consumers, hence the frequency of meter reading acquirement is low, that is, usually once a month. Moreover, with human involvement, it is prone to human errors as well as tampering of records. This leads to non-transparency in the metering system. To devise an efficient metering system, the concept of Automatic Meter Reading (AMR) and Energy Profiling System (EPS) [1-2] originated, which provide an effective means of energy consumption information collection, and its analysis, for accurate billing. A plethora of technologies can be utilized for the implementation of such a system, each having its own pros and cons. Radio frequency based EPS can make use of Handheld, Mobile, and Fixed network. In handheld and touch based EPS, a handheld computer equipped with a transceiver is used (radio frequency or touch) to collect readings, but it does not make optimum use of the AMR capable meters, as meter reading personnel are required. Mobile or Drive-by meter reading is another approach where a reading device is installed in a vehicle. Due to the short range of mobility, it again requires a team for collection of meter readings. AMR can also be implemented by making use of Power Line Communication (PLC) [3-4], but it has an inherent disadvantage of interference and noise, which deems it unreliable. Wi-Fi, ZigBee and 3G technologies [5-6] have also been used for transmission of metering information, but have not being widespread as they require installation of facility/ access points to cover the designated areas and thus do not provide a cost effective solution in existing environments. Our indigenously developed GSM transmission module induce

transparency in the current meter reading system, by facilitating low cost real time monitoring of consumer energy consumption. Automation would lead to an efficient energy metering system by removing human errors. Our system also allows the energy supplier company to remotely control the consumer energy meter. A major feature is the inclusion of a user consumption profiling system, accessible to users and the energy supply company. By incorporating control coupled with profiling, the project aims at creating some degree of awareness among users, encouraging them towards conservation of energy. An additional feature explored is the traffic profiling using Global Positioning System (GPS) to indicating the location of consumers which is extremely beneficial if used in collaboration with sensor circuits to indicate meter theft. Most of these features were not available with system developed.

Dr. D. S. Jangamshetti, and Dr. S. H. Jangamshetti, “Design, Implementation and Testing of Theft and Maintenance Monitoring of Batteries of Stand-alone SPV systems,” IEEE, 2015

Battery management system (BMS) is used in Electric Vehicles (EV) and Energy Storage Systems to monitor and control the charging and discharging of rechargeable batteries. BMS keeps the battery safe and reliable and increases the stability without going into damaging state. The state of the battery is maintained by monitoring voltage, current, and the ambient temperature. For monitoring purpose, data is obtained from various analog/digital sensors and processed through the microcontroller. In the imminent future, Electric Vehicles will be the leading form of transportation. Lithium-based rechargeable batteries will be widely used. These battery

packs will need to be constantly monitored and managed in order to maintain the safety, efficiency and reliability of the whole electric vehicle. A battery management system consists of: (1) a battery level monitoring system (2) optimal charging algorithm and (3) a cell/thermal balancing circuitry. The voltage, current and temperature measurements are used to estimate all crucial states and parameters of the battery system, such as the battery impedance and capacity, state of health, state of charge, and the remaining useful life. The stability of the electrodes depend on the temperature within the cell and its effects on the volatile organic solvents that make up the electrolyte. Selected solvents have a boiling point at 90°C and any increase above 90°C would boil off the solvent. Hence, increasing the cell's internal pressure, and forcing the solvent to vent. Thus preventing such excessive rise in temperature helps preserve the integrity of the cells. It is also affected by the discharge rate and temperature. At the end of the cell's life the actual capacity will be approaching only 80% of its rated capacity. In this case, even if the cell is fully charged, its SOC would only be 80%. For an accurate estimate the ageing and environmental factors have to be taken into account. If the SOC reference is also defined as the current fully charged capacity of the cell, then, the adjustment factors would have to be applied to the rated capacity to determine a new reference capacity .

E. Effah, F. L. Aryeh, “GSM-Based Home Appliances Control System for Domestic Power Users in Ghana” Energy Efficiency, IEEE, 2016.

The rising increase in population and its attendant increase in the consumption of energy, [2] presented the development and

implementation of a Global System for Mobile Communication (GSM) based remote control system for electrical appliances and lighting that enables complete control of the interface on which it is based. The GSM shield was used for receiving short message service (SMS) from the homeowner's mobile that automatically enables an Arduino microcontroller to take the necessary actions like switching OFF and ON electrical appliances. The design system reads the SMS and acts according to the message. In designing a low cost and ubiquitous automated system, [3] developed a compacted short message service (SMS) based on automated hardware controlling system. The designed system developed will send instructions to different circuits, which are specially designed for specific events through hardware controlling system which receives SMS at the GSM modem attached with the server and relates it to the hardware controlling system through parallel port. In the development and implementation of a global system for mobile communication, [4] presented a control system for electrical appliance that enables the complete control of the interface on which it is based. The GSM module control system was used for receiving short message service (SMS) from user's mobile phone that automatically enables the controller to take further action like switching ON and OFF the electrical appliances. The designed system was integrated with microcontroller and GSM network interface using C language with the aid of MPLAB software which was utilized to accomplish the integration. In suggesting two methods for home security, [5] uses web camera and SMS which uses GSM-GPS module. The designed implementation showed that whenever there was a motion in front of the camera, it gives security alert in

terms of sound and a mail is delivered to the owner through SMS which uses sim548c and Atmega644p microcontroller, sensors, relays and buzzers. In the implementation on global system module network by using short message service (SMS), [6] design a system that contains a GSM modem and interfacing unit circuit with microcontrollers. The designed system could control up to eight different electrical devices which are needed in daily life in different area. The system control is actualized by sending a specific SMS messages from traditional or smart phone which is restricted to a pre-defined phone number and are set in the software of the receiver.

F. Abate , “Smart meter for the IoT,” IEEE, 2018.

Electric Energy is a vital resource in everyday life and a backbone to the industry. Being limited its proper use and measurement is very important. Restructuring of power system, penetration of distributed generation and power theft are going to be the key challenges in the near future. The operational information will be crucial for the functioning of the power distribution networks. One of the information sources is going to be the Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI). Smart meter is an advanced energy meter that measures electrical energy consumption and provides additional information as compared to a conventional energy meter. It aims to improve the reliability, quality and security of supply. Integration of AMI into electricity grid needs implementation of a variety of techniques, controls and software, depending on the required features. This paper discusses the need of smart meters, their working, benefits and challenges in implementing them. The paper also presents few case

studies and cost benefit analysis done earlier. The development of human society depends on the proper and wise utilization of all resources whether natural resource or a man-made resource.

Khadijah Alsafwan, Fatimah Alshaer, Lolah Hakami, Khawlah Aseeri, Masoumah AlJishi, Dilek Dustegor, “iTrack: A Residential Energy Monitoring System Tailored to Meet Local Needs,” IC, 2015.

t—Saudi Arabia has encountered a great economic growth in oil and gas resources in the past decades, and if domestic consumption rates continue in their current pathways, it is expected that there will be a contraction in oil exports, which will negatively affect Saudi Arabia's ability in the future to maintain the current high levels of spending in both investment and consumption. Residential consumption in Saudi Arabia accounts for 51% of total electricity sold in 2012. Therefore, targeting private residencies will reduce both the amount of fuel needed to generate electricity and the amount of greenhouse gases. This project aims to build a smart home system. This system will monitor and analyze the energy consumption, utilize lights when needed, program the temperature by keeping your house warmer than normal when you are away and setting the temperature as high as comfortable if needed. Then display the information to improve customer awareness by using colored LEDs to alert customers to different parameters, and turn their loads on and off based on the cost of electricity use as well as enable consumers to control some of their home appliances usage through a mobile application to reduce electricity usage and minimize energy waste. The use of energy has been a key in the development of the human society by helping to adapt to the environment. Energy is the main source of income in Saudi Arabia, and the world relies heavily on oil as a major source of energy.

Savita, Sumit Shrivastava, Abhishek Arora, Vikas Varshney, “Overvoltage and Undervoltage Protection of Load using GSM modem SMS Alert,” IEEE, 2018.

The on-time delay circuit not only protects the load from switching surges but also from quick changeover (off and on) effect of over/ Here is an inexpensive auto cut-off circuit, which is fabricated using transistor and other discrete components. It can be used to protect loads such as refrigerator, T.V., and VCR from undesirable over and under line voltages, as well as surges caused due to sudden failure/resumption of main power supply. This circuit can be used directly as a standalone circuit between the mains supply and the load, or it may be inserted between an existing automatic/manual stabilizer and the load. The over/under voltage cut-off with ON-Time delay provides various types of protection. Over-voltage protection. Under-voltage protection. Protection against transients. Protection to load from frequent turning ON & OFF by providing time delay . Here is an inexpensive auto cutoff circuit, which is fabricated using transistors and other discrete components.

Block diagram

LDR SENSOR

LDR (Light Dependent Resistor) as the name states is a special type of resistor that works on the photoconductivity principle means that resistance changes according to the intensity of light. Its resistance decreases with an increase in the intensity of light. It is often used as a light sensor, light meter, [Automatic street light](#), and in areas where we need to have light sensitivity. LDR is also known as a Light Sensor. LDR are usually available in 5mm, 8mm, 12mm, and 25mm dimensions.

RELAY MODULE

Relay modules are simply circuit boards that house one or more relays. They come in a variety of shapes and sizes, but are most commonly rectangular with 2, 4, or 8 relays mounted on them, sometimes even up to a 16 relays.

Relay modules contain other components than the relay unit. These include [indicator LEDs](#), [protection diodes](#), transistors, resistors, and other parts. But what is the module relay, which makes the bulk of the device? You may ask. Here are facts to note about it:

- A relay is an electrical switch that can be used to control devices and systems that use higher voltages. In the case of module relay, the mechanism is typically an [electromagnet](#).
- The relay module input voltage is usually DC. However, the electrical load that a relay will control can be either AC or DC, but essentially within the limit levels that the relay is designed for.
- A relay module is available in an array of input voltage ratings: It can be a 3.2V or 5V relay module for low power switching, or it can be a 12 or 24V relay module for heavy-duty systems.
- The relay module information is normally printed on the surface of the device for ready reference. This includes the input voltage rating, switch voltage, and current limit.

ESP8266

The ESP8266 is a low-cost Wi-Fi microchip, with a full TCP/IP stack and microcontroller capability, produced by Espressif Systems[1] in Shanghai, China. The chip first came to the attention of Western makers in August 2014 with the ESP-01 module, made by a third-

party manufacturer Ai-Thinker. This small module allows microcontrollers to connect to a Wi-Fi network and make simple TCP/IP connections using Hayes-style commands. However, at first there was almost no English-language documentation on the chip and the commands it accepted.[2] The very low price and the fact that there were very few external components on the module, which suggested that it could eventually be very inexpensive in volume, attracted many hackers to explore the module, the chip, and the software on it, as well as to translate the Chinese documentation.[3] The ESP8285 is an ESP8266 with 1 MiB of built-in flash, allowing the building of single-chip devices capable of connecting to Wi-Fi.[4] The successors to these microcontroller chips is the ESP32 family of chips, including the pin-compatible ESP32-C3.

RFID READER

Active RFID and Passive RFID technologies, while often considered and evaluated together, are fundamentally distinct technologies with substantially different capabilities. In most cases, neither technology provides a complete solution for supply chain asset management applications. Rather, the most effective and complete supply chain solutions leverage the

advantages of each technology and combine their use in complementary ways. This need for both technologies must be considered by RFID standards initiatives to effectively meet the requirements of the user community.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the suggested web-based energy monitoring system utilising IoT technology and various hardware elements such as Raspberry Pi Pico, LCD display, current coil, relay, energy metre PZEM004T, ESP8226, and RFID is a practical and affordable solution for tracking energy usage in residential homes. The device enables homeowners to keep an eye on their energy usage in real-time and offers insights into their habits, enabling them to find ways to cut their electricity costs. On the LCD panel, the system also shows the electricity tariff that was calculated based on energy consumption. The gear works in unison to measure and monitor the energy usage, and the ESP8226 module wirelessly transmits the data to the Raspberry Pi Pico, which analyses and stores it. By managing the power supply to the energy metre and the relay, the relay makes sure that the essential parts are turned on when they are required. An RFID card reader is employed to verify the user's identity and guarantee that only approved users can access the system. This adds another level of security to the system. This web-based energy monitoring system provides households with a useful and effective way to keep track of their energy usage, lower their electricity costs, and support a more sustainable future.

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